

THE PROBLEM OF TEXTBOOK QUALITY IN MODERN EDUCATION

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Abstract. *The article raises the problem of young people's disinterest in reading books. The article describes the actual errors in textbooks on Russian literature. A suggestion is given about the reasonableness in the choice of literary texts for inclusion in the school curriculum.*

Keywords: *education, fiction, young generation, professionalism, competence, academic knowledge, accessibility.*

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, the problem of education has become a stumbling block to achieving one of the main goals – building a free, democratic and prosperous state [5, 56].

Reflecting on this issue, about the interest of the younger generation in education, about the loss of passion for reading books, about the passive attitude to cultural events, we come to a vicious circle.

The entire education system is based on the following principle: pre-school education, then school (elementary and high school), higher education, master's degree, doctoral studies, etc. The University's task is to educate a decent, knowledgeable professional specialist, who in turn should be able to train aspiring schoolchildren or students of colleges and lyceums. And so it is in every field, in every specialty.

It is not surprising that when graduates who do not meet modern requirements graduate from universities and at the same time take on the responsibility of educating the younger generation, the result is obvious: students who are not ready to receive and accept academic knowledge sit at the desks of higher educational institutions.

METHODS AND MATERIALS

As teachers who worry about the well-being of their country, we became interested in the question: what is the reason for the current state of the education system, which is not always able to keep up with the times and meet its modern needs?

In order to be more objective in answering the problem, we asked this question to schoolchildren and students. Everyone answered with one voice – lack of time. And the reason for this problem, according to the same youth, is the Internet. We would make some adjustments, noting that, most likely, this is the dominance of social networks. So far, the younger generation, which is not responsible for the family, for loved ones, not burdened with domestic and social problems, is not able to set priorities correctly and allocate time usefully.

Undoubtedly, there are other factors that slow down the interest of young people in education and the desire to become professional specialists. And the solution of many of them no longer depends on the teachers.

Therefore, in our case, I would like to note the disadvantages that directly depend on scientists and teachers.

Russian literature textbooks (part 1) by N.M. Mirkurbanova, G.F. Goleva [6, 7], textbook on Russian literature for the 9th grade (parts 1 and 2) by G.T. Garipova, N.M. Petrukhina [2, 3], textbook on literature for 5th grades by Sergeeva N.I., Merkina G.S. [7].

RESULTS

A thorough analysis of the textbooks presented, first of all, showed unfair compilation of textbooks. For example, in the textbook on literature for the 9th grade, p. 35, it is indicated that the main themes of the comedy "The Minor" are "the theme of serfdom and its influence on landowners and domestic servants", "the theme of the fatherland and service to it", "the theme of education and the theme of the morals of the court nobility" [2, 35]. It is noted that all these topics are very topical. In the same textbook, on page 57, it is indicated that in the comedy "Woe from Wit" by A.S. Griboyedov touches upon such issues as "serfdom, education, upbringing, civic duty and service" [2, 57], their relevance is particularly noted.

It is difficult to make out how one writer differs from another, Derzhavin from Lomonosov, Pushkin from Lermontov, and Onegin from Pechorin. Here are two quotes in which we omitted the names of the authors and characters:

"The aimlessness of existence, spiritual emptiness leads to the fact that ... he becomes an "extra person" in society. And that's his tragedy. ... he created a truthful, typical image that reflected the essential features of an entire generation."

"... I tried to give in the image ... a typical generalization of a characteristic phenomenon in the life of a modern society... Skepticism and disappointment ... "this is a reflection of the general state that encompassed a significant part of the noble intelligentsia at the beginning of the century".

Without knowing who they are talking about, is it possible to determine from these quotes, which are peculiar conclusions about Onegin and Pechorin, which heroes are mentioned in these quotes?

Further, in the textbook on literature for 5th grade by N.I. Sergeeva, G.S. Merkin, in the "Fairy Tales" section, the biography of Hans Christian Andersen is given in such a complex and confusing language [7, 97-101] that it is difficult to understand the information provided not only by 5th grade students, but also by older children.

For example, G.H. Andersen's fairy tale "The Little Mermaid" is offered for 5th grade students [7, 101], which is difficult to understand, and the fascinating and accessible fairy tale "Flint" is excluded from the program.

In the 6th grade, the Slavic "Myth of the Sun" has a non-dynamic plot and uninteresting events [8, 9].

From the Tale of Bygone Years, instead of the "Tale of Kozhemyak" [8, 35], the "Tale of Olga" is suggested.

In the 9th grade, the novel "Poor People" was proposed from the works of F.M. Dostoevsky [3, 44]. Although it would be much more interesting to get acquainted with the novel "The Brothers Karamazov".

DISCUSSION

At first glance, it may seem that there is no problem. But how can we educate young people to be truthful and decent if false information is already allowed in school textbooks?

In almost all literature textbooks, the analysis of works and biographies of writers is given in dry and schematic language: it is difficult to distinguish one work from another and one writer from the other. The biographies of such extraordinary personalities as Lermontov and Pushkin are virtually identical: they were born, wrote their brilliant works and died.

In the case of the works of D. Fonvizin "The Minor" and the comedy of A.S. Griboyedov "The Minor", it should be noted that these characteristics do not distinguish at all between two remarkable works and the work of two completely dissimilar writers.

Special attention should also be paid to the fact that in textbooks on natural sciences: zoology, biology, chemistry, the material is copied from academic scientific works, which is beyond the power of students to understand.

Assignments and questions are compiled in such a way that it is impossible to find answers in the presented material after the text.

Not all fiction texts in literature textbooks, starting from 5th grade, are entertaining and age-appropriate.

CONCLUSION

Thus, from school, students have lost interest in learning and passion for books.

We, teachers of higher educational institutions, face the same problem when textbooks of a theoretical nature on linguistics and literary studies contain some materials in an inaccessible and incomprehensible language. In this case, a huge responsibility is imposed on both the university teacher and the school teacher, whose task is to process educational materials for a more accessible explanation.

There is another very important factor, which is not denied by the youth themselves – the control over the educational process of the younger generation by their parents. Unfortunately, time is developing in such a way that most of the parents are outside the Republic, or in search of a decent salary, they are forced to work in several places.

Since 2020, large-scale work has been carried out in the Republic of Uzbekistan to review new school textbooks from grades 1 to 11, both for Russian classes and for national ones. For this purpose, school teachers and university professors were involved.

Unfortunately, the textbooks that have already been published have a major drawback related to the correspondence between scheduled hours and actually allocated hours.

Russian textbooks in national classrooms are designed for 68 hours (68 lessons), but in fact schools allocate 34 hours (34 lessons) for teaching Russian. This means that teachers are forced to go through two topics in one lesson, which significantly reduces the level of assimilation of knowledge. But this is the next problem that needs to be solved.

Thus, all of the above factors indicate that the solution to the problems mentioned above is assigned to each of us.

The quality and high level of education depend both on the compilers of textbooks, school and university teachers, as well as on the students themselves and their parents.

REFERENCES

1. Blok A. Izbrannoe. – M.: Pravda, 1978.
2. Garipova G.T., Petruhina N.M. Uchebnik-hrestomatiya po russkoj literature. 9 klass. Chast' I. - Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2014.

3. Garipova G.T., Petruhina N.M. Uchebnik-hrestomatiya po russkoj literature. 9 klass. Chast' II. - Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2014.
4. Gribredov A.S. Gore ot uma. – L.: Detskaya literatura, 1971.
5. Mirziyoev Sh.M. My vse vmeste postroim svobodnoe, demokraticeskoe i procvetayushchee gosudarstvo Uzbekistan. – Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2016.
6. Mirkurbanov N.M, Goleva G.F. Uchebnik dlya 10 klassa. Literatura. Chast' I. – Tashkent, 2017.
7. Sergeeva N.I., Merkin G.S. Literatura. 5 klass. – Tashkent: SHARQ, 2015.
8. Styrkas I.N., Abdullaeva G.Sh., Tumparov R.R. Literatura. Uchebnik-hrestomatiya dlya 6 klassa. – Tashkent: SHARQ, 2013.